

Factors affecting teacher performance

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to see whether there is an influence of school principal leadership, organizational culture, and teacher competence on teacher performance. Another aim was to see how much influence these factors have on teacher performance either partially or simultaneously. The research used a quantitative approach with survey methods. Analysis of the data used was multiple regression. Participants involved in the study were 385 teachers in Bandung high school by using proportional stratified random sampling. The results of the study showed that there was a significant influence on the school principal leadership variables, organizational culture, and teacher competence on teacher performance. Statistically the amount of contribution from all independent variables was 68.12%, so the remaining 32.88% was determined by other variables not measured in the study. This research was also useful to find out the factors that can improve teacher performance, so that it is expected to be a theoretical or practical consideration in schools in order to improve the quality of teachers and schools.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Education is one of the important factors in the development of a nation [1]. High or low quality of education is not only caused by the educational process, but can also be influenced by the low performance of teachers as educators. Performance is the result and work behavior that has been achieved in order to complete the tasks and responsibilities that have been given within a certain period of time [2]. Since long time ago, scientists and the government have considered teachers as a major asset in educating students [3]. Because in the world of education, the relationship between students and teachers becomes an important factor in learning and teaching activities, both in gaining knowledge and in developing the personality of students [4]. Therefore, the government has made teacher reform a goal in the context of improving education in Indonesia [5].

The quality of teachers in Indonesia is still low, both in terms of competence, knowledge, and pedagogical expertise [6]. The Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) survey in 2018 has released that the quality of Indonesian education is still in the 10th lowest category, both in the fields of literacy, science and mathematics [7]. This is due to the disparity and low quality of teachers. With the low quality of the teacher, it will have an impact on various things, including achievement and learning process for students. Because teachers play an important role in regulating the learning environment that makes students active in learning activities [8].

Based on Law No. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System that educators and education staff are obliged to: i) create a meaningful, fun, creative, dynamic and dialogical educational atmosphere; ii) have a professional commitment to improve the quality of education; and iii) set an example and maintain the good name of the institution, profession and position in accordance with the trust given to it. Teachers also play a role in influencing both inside and outside the school environment. In addition, to create a good education system requires collaboration and mutual support between the principal, teachers and students [9]. Previous studies have shown that one of the factors that influences student learning success is collaboration between students, teachers, and other parties involved in school activities [8].

The quality of the teacher's performance as a professional is an important thing to discuss, considering its significant role on student achievement [10]. But this role cannot be separated from the educational context, student characteristics, and school factors [11]. In addition, the ability of teachers to be confident, create a comfortable climate for students, maintain interaction and maintain contact with students can increase student involvement in learning [12]. Teacher instructional qualities such as classroom management and cognitive activation also affect students' motivation to learn [13].

Internal and external factors also influence the success of teachers in order to improve performance. Internally, the quality of a teacher determines student achievement [14]. The quality of a good teacher will certainly determine how students get knowledge. A good competency of a power teacher goes linear with the achievements of students [14]. Teacher competence is a set of skills, knowledge, and behaviors that must be possessed and mastered by teachers in carrying out their professional duties as teaching staff [15]. Understanding a teacher of technology also affects the quality of teaching. The mastery of the integration of science and technology is determined by the knowledge possessed by teachers and their openness to technology. This ability then becomes the teacher's own competence to improve the quality and learning outcomes [16].

Internal factors such as teacher psychology should also be considered as their influence on teacher performance. Emotional intelligence and self-efficacy are said to be very significantly related to teacher performance [17]. A teacher with high emotional intelligence and social skills, tends to have better classroom management skills [18]. Self-efficacy and job involvement are also highly correlated with worker performance [19]. Teachers who have conscientiousness personality are also mentioned as influential and predictors of their performance [20].

Externally, the school has several devices, one of which is the principal. The success of a teacher's performance is certainly determined by the level or intervention of school principals or leadership in schools which is certainly mediated by variables such as self-efficacy, commitment, and job satisfaction [21]. Leadership can be understood in the school environment as a process of influencing teachers and students through teaching and learning, conveying knowledge, skills, values, culture and ideas [22]. The role given by schools through empowerment and enhancing teacher quality programs can also affect the performance, commitment, and behavior of their membership in schools [23]. In addition, the organizational climate and collaboration of various parties that support the continuity of teaching are important factors in order to improve teacher performance [24].

The influence of organizational culture in schools can also be a variable that can affect teacher performance in schools [25]. Organizational culture is defined as a system that contains shared meanings and values shared by all members of the organization that distinguishes the organization from other organizations [26]. Organizational conditions can affect the performance of teachers in schools and that performance will improve if moderated by the acceptance or attachment of teachers to schools owned. The higher the comfort of the teacher with the school can increase its influence on their performance in the school [27]. While the pressure experienced by a teacher in a school that is sourced from various things and aspects will certainly reduce performance [28].

In previous studies, leadership and organizational culture correlated positively and influenced teacher performance [29]. Hasan [30] in his research also mentioned that work motivation, school principal leadership, and organizational culture were predictors of teacher performance. In addition, teacher performance and school principal leadership are positively correlated and significantly influence teacher performance [31]. Likewise, organizational culture and teacher competence are positively correlated and affect teacher performance [32]. In connection with the description, the problem affecting performance is the implementation of the certification program, and competence is influenced by the leadership of the school principal and organizational culture as presented in Figure 1.

Based on the previous study, no research has been found that discusses the influence of principal leadership, organizational culture, and teacher competence on teacher performance together. Researchers also have not found research examining the variables in senior high schools in Bandung, Indonesia. It is hoped that the results of this study can be used by educational institutions, especially in Bandung, Indonesia to improve teacher performance as the main resource in schools.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework of research

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. Participant

This research employed proportional stratified random sampling technique. This is a method of selecting the sample size of a population where each member of the population has the same opportunity and all the possible mergers selected as a sample have the same opportunity. There were 385 teachers from Bandung City High School, Cimahi City, West Bandung District, Indonesia selected as the research sample.

Table 1 shows that in terms of gender the number of male respondents was 41.82%, while female respondents were 58.12%. Thus, the characteristics of teachers who are respondents are more women than male respondents. For the age of respondents, the most respondents were aged 46 to 50 years by 19.48%, while the least were respondents aged over 50 years by 11.43%. At the education level of respondents, where the Characteristics of respondents based on undergraduate education amounted to 211 people or 54.81%, who have a master degree amounted to 172 or amounted to 44.67%, and educated doctor of 2 or equal to .51%. While for the majority of respondents' tenure with 11 years to 15 years, there were 96 people or 24.94%, while the lowest number of respondents who had 1 year to 5 years period was 62 teachers or 16.11%.

Table 1. Participant demographic data

No	Category	Amount	Percentage (%)
1	Gender		
	Men	161	41.82
	Woman	224	58.18
2	Level of education		
	Bachelor	211	54.81
	Master	172	44.67
	Doctor	2	.52
3	Age		
	25-30 year	62	16.11
	31-35 year	65	16.88
	36-40 year	72	18.70
	41-45 year	67	17.40
	46-50 year	75	19.48
	>50 year	44	11.43
4	Length of work		
	1-5 year	62	16.11
	6-10 year	63	16.36
	11-15 year	96	24.94
	16-20 year	81	21.04
	>20 year	83	21.55

2.2. Instruments

The questionnaire about the principal's leadership consists of 22 indicators and compiled based on Ministry of Education Decree No. 16 of 2007 with dimensions: i) educator, ii) manager, iii) administrator, iv) supervisor, v) leaders, vi) innovators, vii) motivators. The questionnaire about organizational culture was compiled based on Luthan's theory [8] which consisted of 19 indicators with dimensions: i) behavioral regulations, ii) norms, iii) value of confidence, iv) philosophy, v) terms and conditions, and vi) organizational climate. Questionnaire on teacher competencies consisting of 16 indicators and compiled based on Minister of National Education Regulations No. 16 of 2007 with dimensions: i) pedagogic competence, ii) personality competence, iii) social competence, iv) professional competence. Teachers' performance is arranged based on

Ministry of Education Decree No. 14 of 2005 and consists of 15 indicators with dimensions: i) educate, ii) teach, iii) guide, iv) train, v) direct, vi) assess, and vii) evaluate. A validity test was conducted to test whether a measuring instrument is valid or not.

The questionnaire about the principal's leadership consisted of 22 indicators with eight dimensions that were declared valid because the r count value was greater than the critical value which was .300. The organizational culture questionnaire consisted of 19 indicators with six dimensions that were declared valid because the r count value was greater than the critical value which was .300. The teacher competency questionnaire consisted of 16 indicators with three dimensions that were declared valid because the r count value was greater than the critical value which was .300. The questionnaire about teacher performance consists of 15 indicators with three dimensions that are declared valid because the r count value is greater than the critical value which is .300.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The normality test results with the SPSS program are as in the normality test as shown in Table 2, which shows that the normality test data in studies that have been previously tested with the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. Based on the test results with a significance level of 0.05, where the significance obtained from the processing results for all research variables is greater than the significance level value, then the data to measure the research variables show insignificant results or accept H_0 , meaning that the sample data originates from populations that are normally distributed or there is no difference between sample data from populations that are normally distributed [33]. Table 3 shows the largest correlation is between the principal leadership and teacher competence variables (correlation value of .764). The second largest correlation is the correlation between principal leadership and organizational culture with a correlation value of .695.

Table 2. Normality test result

		Principal leadership	Organizational culture	Teacher competency	Teacher performance
N		385	385	385	385
Normal parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	73.0443	60.1429	61.4494	48.6104
	Std. Deviation	16.40981	14.04690	13.31932	10.57409
Most extreme difference	Absolute	.079	.057	.037	.053
	Positive	.046	.054	.036	.049
	Negative	-.079	-.057	-.037	-.053
Test statistic		0.79	.057	.037	.053
Asymp. Sig. (2-Tailed)		.063	.098	.200	.107

Table 3. Sub-structural regression test result

		Principal leadership	Organizational culture	Teacher competency
Leadership	Pearson correlation	1	.695**	.764**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	385	385	385
School culture	Pearson correlation	.695**	1	.669**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	385	385	385
Teacher competency	Pearson correlation	.764**	.669**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	385	385	385

**Significant at 1%

Based on SPSS calculation as shown in Table 4, the F count value is 271.344, where the rejection criteria H_0 if F count is greater than F table with free degrees $v_1=k-1=2$ and $v_2=385-3=382$ and 95% confidence level, then from the distribution table F is obtained table for F .05,3,385=3.0193. Due to 271.344 is greater than 3.0193, H_0 is rejected. It means that there is a simultaneous relationship between principal leadership, organizational culture, and teacher competence on teacher performance. It can be interpreted that there is a joint influence between principal leadership, organizational culture, and teacher competence on teacher performance.

Table 4. Result of F test

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	29246.839	3	9748.946	271.334	.000*
	Residual	13688.720	381	35.928		
	Total	42935.558	384			

a. Dependent variable: Teacher performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), teacher competency, organizational culture, principal leadership

Based on the results of the analysis of the influence of the principal's leadership variable has a total influence on teacher performance by 35.78%, thus the influence of the principal's leadership on the teacher's performance gives a significant effect, where the biggest influence. This means that teacher performance will depend on the leadership ability of the principal. Kreitner and Angelo [34] state that effective leadership influences followers to have the desire and skills to produce effective actions. This will encourage the performance of subordinates. The type of leadership applied by schools also significantly influences teacher performance, previous research suggests that the type of transformational or democratic leadership correlates positively with teacher performance [35]. With good leadership accompanied by the ability to manage the organization will have a positive impact on the performance of its members [36].

Based on the results of the analysis of the magnitude of the influence of school culture variables have a total effect on teacher performance by 7.81%, thus the influence of school culture on teacher performance gives a significant effect, where the effect is the smallest. This means that teacher performance will depend on the conductivity and good culture of the school. The results of this study, in accordance with the reality in the field, based on field observations, that the performance of high school teachers in the City/Regency of Bandung, West Bandung Regency, and Cimahi City is strongly influenced by conductivity and the merits of the school culture.

Robbins [26] states that one of the functions of organizational culture is to facilitate and strengthen employee performance improvement both in the short and long term. In addition, according to Yukl [37], high performance can only be achieved if the work culture is conducive and dynamic. Rivai [38] also states that a dynamic and conducive organizational culture will shape a productive work culture, which encourages employee/teacher performance improvement. Through cultural understanding it is built through many interrelated elements, the school can build a community that will support the workplace by providing a social context that can stimulate teacher performance changes [39]. Culture is indeed seen as a way of life and excellence in an organization that binds and influences what they think about themselves and their work, so that it greatly influences their performance [40].

Based on the analysis of the magnitude of the effect of the variable teacher competence has a total effect on teacher performance by 24.53%, thus the effect of teacher competence on teacher performance has a significant effect, where the second largest influence. This means that teacher performance will depend on the level of teacher competency. The results of this study, in accordance with the reality in the field, based on field observations, that the performance of Rivai [38], there are 18 competencies that are commonly found in various types of occupations, namely: achievement orientation, analytical thinking, conceptual thinking, customer service orientation, developing others, directiveness, flexibility, impact and influence, information seeking, initiative, integrity, interpersonal understanding, organizational awareness, organizational commitment, relationship building, self-confidence, team leadership, teamwork and cooperation. Based on previous research, competence has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance. This means that higher competencies can improve teacher performance. Because the competence of the teacher will affect the management and how to teach in the classroom [41]-[43].

Based on the results of the analysis of the magnitude of the influence of the principal's leadership variables, organizational culture, and teacher competence have a total influence on teacher performance of 68.12% thus the influence of the three independent variables on teacher performance gives a very significant effect. The effect of other variables that affect teacher performance, but not examined, the effect is 31.88%. The variables are: teacher motivation, infrastructure, communication, cooperation, and others. This means that teacher performance will depend on the leadership ability of the principal. The results of this study, in accordance with the reality in the field, based on field observations, that the performance of high school teachers in the City/Regency of Bandung, West Bandung Regency, and Cimahi City is strongly influenced by the three dominant variables. If you want to improve teacher performance, then optimize the existence of these three variables, the principal's leadership, organizational culture and teacher competence.

4. CONCLUSION

This study concluded that simultaneously, principal leadership, organizational culture, and teacher competence affect teacher performance positively and significantly. This means that the higher the independent variable in this study, the higher the teacher performance variable. Overall, the three independent variables have a great contribution, so that they can be considered in the field to pay attention to these three variables in determining teacher performance.

This study has major implications for institutions in order to consider the various independent variables that exist as important factors that must be considered to support teacher performance. Future research should be able to further explore other psychological variables that are not widely identified at this time. The addition and heterogeneity of more samples can also increase the quality of the expected results.

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